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Evaluation On Regional Boarding Schools In Terms Of Management And Educational Processes

Fatih Çağatay BAZ

Osmaniye Korkut Ata University, Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences,
Management Information Systems, Adana/Türkiye
fatihcagataybaz@osmaniye.edu.tr, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6398-9851>

Ayhan YILDIRIM

Ministry of Education,
ayhanyildrm@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3425-2076>

Abstract

There have been rapid developments in many areas in recent years. Technology, management, education and similar fields affect each other. The fact that lifestyles create new situations during the Covid 19 pandemic has made it necessary to conduct research in many fields according to different variables. Especially in terms of management and education processes, regional boarding schools are an area where few studies have been conducted in Turkey. In this sense, this study is important. The aim of this study is to evaluate the regional boarding schools opened to meet the educational needs of school-age children in rural Turkey in terms of management and education processes. It has been observed that regional boarding schools in Turkey contribute positively to educational equality in terms of access to education of children living in rural areas and contribute to their academic perseverance. As a result of the literature, it has been determined that the problem of inequality stems from problems related to being away from the family, that there are schools that do not meet certain standards among boarding schools, and that some students cannot achieve academic success for this reason. As a result of the literature review conducted within the scope of the study, it was observed that there was not enough research on the subject. In this context, first of all, information about regional boarding schools was given in line with the information obtained on the subject, and then the problems they faced were tried to be explained. In other parts of the study, the importance of regional boarding secondary schools in success and regional boarding secondary schools in the Turkish education system are explained.

Keywords: Management, Education System, Regional Boarding Schools.

1.INTRODUCTION

The differences in population in Turkey have been realized by moving from rural to urban areas since the proclamation of the Republic. Although the rural population constituted a large part of the total population in the 1920s, today this situation is moving in the opposite direction. Similarly, while the number of schools in villages decreased, the number of schools in cities increased. As a result of this situation, it is known that various options have been developed to meet the educational needs of rural areas. In these sparsely populated regions, the educational needs of primary school students were met with regional boarding schools and bussed education, and the said services were carried out with a combined classroom application in places where bussed education was not available (Demirtaş, 2007; Aydın et al., 2018).

Regional Boarding School is expressed as institutions that provide education by taking students from residential areas where the population is low and dispersed and where there is no school. There have been changes over time in regional boarding schools that provide education in line with certain conditions. With the circular published in 2012, it was decided to accept only secondary school students in the boarding areas of regional schools, but due to geographical conditions and insufficient schools, this practice could not be fully implemented. The scope and quality of the education services provided in regional boarding schools are a matter of debate.

Academic success is defined as the level of realization of the behaviors targeted in the school life of the students. The results of some researches have reflected that variables such as anxiety, self-efficacy, and loneliness perception have an effect on academic achievement. As a result of the researches, it has been obtained that the academic perseverance of the students studying in normal primary schools is higher, and the students studying in regional boarding schools are lower. In addition to those who see the early departure from the family environment of students studying in boarding schools as the main reason for failure, there are also those who attribute their failure to the characteristics of teaching practices. However, one of the aims of the education system, which aims to make the people in the society happier and more compatible with their environment, is the success of these people (Çetinkaya & Developer, Gönül & Arslan, 2018; 2013; Gürbey et al., 2020).

One of the main problems of the education system in Turkey has been the provision of education services to compulsory education students living in rural areas where there are no open schools or where there are very few students. In Turkey, the targeted level of success has not been achieved in keeping schools open and assigning teachers to these schools, especially in rural areas. For this reason, the establishment of boarding schools has been widely practiced since the first years of the Republic of Turkey in order to solve the access problem.

Following the extension of compulsory education to eight years in Turkey, schools were divided into three groups as bussed, regular and boarding schools. Boarding schools and boarding schools gained particular value during this period and their numbers started to increase rapidly (Dağlı &

Gündüz, 2008). In order to solve the problem of access to education for students living in rural areas, besides the opening of boarding schools, transportation education has also been implemented (Aydoğdu & Dilekmen, 2016). It has also been observed that after the closure of the primary education department of regional boarding schools in 2012, bussed education began to be emphasized instead of boarding education.

In line with the information obtained in this context, it can be stated that regional boarding schools have a great impact on the academic determination of the students. It has been observed that this application, which was created in order to eliminate the problems experienced in the transportation of the students to the school environment and to encourage the students to receive education, brought problems with it. At the beginning of these problems, being separated from the family and some problems that come to the fore come to the fore.

1.1. Regional Boarding Schools

Regional boarding schools are schools established to meet the educational needs of school-age children in villages, hamlets, municipalities and towns where the population is low and scattered. In these schools, students stay away from their families and are educated as boarding schools. In addition to education, students are provided with opportunities such as food, beverage and accommodation (Çetin, 2013). Boarding schools were established in 1958 as "regional boys' boarding school" and started education life in March 1959 with nine boarding students from Afghanistan. In the 1963-1964 academic year, female boarding students started to be admitted for the first time in the Mustafabeyli Town of the Ceyhan District of Adana, and the foundations of the Regional Boarding Primary School and the Pension Primary School were laid. The establishment of regional boarding schools first started in the east and southeast, and 32 regional schools were brought into education in 1964. In these schools, not only literacy education was given, but also art, agriculture and animal husbandry education. Trade and health courses were opened, and besides reading and writing, the opportunity to acquire a profession was also provided (Demirtaş, 2007).

In 1997, in Article 9 of the Primary Education and Education Law No. 222, "In places where the population is small or scattered; By grouping the villages, primary education regional schools and hostels affiliated to them can be opened in the centralized or suitable villages, and in places where grouping is not possible, regional primary boarding schools or mobile schools can be opened. In cities and towns, boarding or boarding schools can be established as needed." Boarding schools continued to be established within the scope of the provision. In addition, the establishment and expansion of boarding schools continued within the scope of Article 25 of the National Education Law No. 1739 and Article 9 of the Primary Education and Education Law No. 222 (Şenol & Yıldız, 2009).

With the establishment of the eight-year compulsory education, the importance of these schools increased in the 1997-1998 academic year and their numbers were increased and they became more

common. With the entry into force of the Law No. 4306 dated 18.06.1997, the establishment of YİBO and PIO gained momentum. However, due to the same services offered, PIOs were differentiated as "Regional Boarding Primary School" in 2006. However, in 2012, a difference was made in the MEB Primary Education Institutions Regulation with the number 28360 and dated 21.07.012, and the Boarding Primary Education Regional Schools were named "Regional Boarding Secondary Schools".

Providing education opportunities for all people is not equally easy or difficult in all areas of the country. Considering the geographical conditions of Turkey, it is quite difficult for any child to get an education in the place where his/her family is or where he/she wants to be. With the opening of these schools, especially in villages where there is no school, village children who have reached the age of compulsory education and are not included in the scope of bussed education have been educated. The purpose of these schools is to raise hopeful, disciplined people who have the habit of working independently (Senol & Yıldız, 2009; Kazu & Aşkın, 2011; Boydak et al., 2012; Baz & Yıldırım, 2021).

The majority of regional boarding schools are unschooled and established in residential areas that support the expansion of basic education. Thus, it contributed to the provision of opportunities and equal opportunities in education (Açıklım, 2002; Yördem, 2009).

1.1.1. Characteristics of Regional Boarding Secondary Schools

The problems of regional boarding schools reflect many differences compared to other educational institutions (Kılıç, 2001). Regional boarding schools have some unique features. According to Tonka (2018), the most significant differences that distinguish YBO from other schools are listed below:

- While the duration of being at the school is 24 hours, this period is limited to 6-8 hours within the scope of other schools,
- They are known as schools that aim to equip children with life skills for the coming years,
- Students receive a high-quality education in unoccupied classrooms and with well-planned resources,
- Students get more academic efficiency by spending all their time in the school environment,
- Students always have access to their teachers and support staff,
- Students are self-motivated and able to work at the same time,
- Students consider being separated from their families in order to receive education, and in this case, they show more academic perseverance,
- Students are constantly supported by their teachers while they are studying,
- Students learn to operate independently, take responsibility and traditional values,

- Students can spend more time on their homework,
- Students can use their time more efficiently by participating in activities outside the education program,
- Students learn to be self-sufficient by performing non-scheduled tasks such as spending their money in the right place, washing and ironing,
- Students can achieve better academic success with the structured lifestyle in the school,
- By taking part in a continuous environment, students can discipline themselves and form good study habits for the future.

As explained in the section above, life in regional boarding schools continues 24 hours a day with the management staff, instructors and students. While regional boarding schools offer many advantages, the problems encountered should also be taken into account.

1.1.2. Problems Faced by Regional Boarding Secondary Schools

In the literature, there are studies on the current situation or problems of regional boarding schools. Some of these studies focus on the general or administrative problems of boarding schools (Aydın & Köroğlu, 2009; Çetinkaya & Gelişli, 2013), while others focus on the psychosocial status of the students in these schools and their satisfaction with their school life (Karataş, 2006; Gökyer, 2011; Yılmaz). & Supervisor, 2012; Nigar, 2014). Since the study was handled within the scope of academic perseverance, the results of studies on management problems such as hostel management of regional boarding schools were excluded from the study, and the study was prepared depending on the problems and educational processes of regional boarding schools related to students. Previous research on regional boarding schools has revealed that the problems in these schools are not due to education, but to the fact that the schools are boarding schools (Demirtaş, 2007).

It is claimed that regional boarding schools have advantages and disadvantages, as well as being a home for students (Çetinkaya & Gelişli, 2013). Regional boarding schools gathered together the places where students study, eat, spend time and sleep. Students spend 24 hours in the school. The place and time of all activities are fixed, and students' days are often repetitive, so it can become a boring routine (Demirel & Türker, 2021). On the other hand, students in boarding schools can allocate more time to lessons and homework thanks to the additional school time, discipline and guidance intensity. It has been noticed that such a situation affects students' academic determination positively (Ceylan & Ünder, 2022). In this context, when various studies are examined; There are many negative consequences for boarding students such as severe psychosomatic disorders, weakening of sibling relationships, damage to family relationships, physical and mental disorders due to severe homesickness or the feeling of not being wanted by the family, rejection, and these can cause academic failure. In this case, the academic determination of the child begins to decrease (Demirel & Türker, 2021; Nigar, 2014). Some studies have stated that some families send their

children to boarding school, at least not to starve, due to poverty and the large number of children (Çetinkaya & Gelişli, 2013).

Some studies have shown that staying away from the family and home environment of the students studying in regional boarding schools may lead to a decrease in their academic perseverance and problems such as anger, aggression or introversion (Arı, 2000; Halıcı, 2005). Nigar (2014) discussed in his study that the subjective well-being levels and satisfaction levels of basic psychological needs of in-house students are lower than those of foreign students. At the same time, he states that raising children away from the love of their parents at a young age causes psychological problems on children and negatively affects their academic success. On the other hand, the main problem of boarding schools is the appointment or assignment of inexperienced teachers, who do not know the needs of children studying in boarding schools, to the regional boarding school (Kılıç, 2001).

Children who are educated within the scope of boarding schools may have less knowledge about life, may not be aware of life's problems and may be isolated from their parents compared to children who are educated at home. Lack of family love can lead to negative personality traits in children. The negative effects of boarding schools can be so great that the benefits of these schools are ineffective.

Students who spend the whole day in an artificial environment, isolated from society, outside of their real place of residence, may have less information about life than students at home. It is noticed that in-house students are detached from their most natural needs, the love of family, and their opportunities to communicate with people of different ages, genders and professionals are also limited. It is observed that all these situations have a negative effect on the academic achievement of children (Arı, 2000).

In addition to the disadvantages, there are also advantages of studying in boarding schools for students. In addition to many educational, social and personal development activities offered by boarding schools, students can develop academically, artistically and athletically by participating in out-of-school trips and observations. As a result of these, there are also studies reflecting that children's self-confidence increases and their skills of recognizing and expressing their own selves improve. Again, children studying in boarding schools develop positive behaviors such as being able to stand on their own feet, establishing healthy communication with their environment, socializing and obeying the rules (Beklevic, 2004; Toksoy, 2009).

Regional boarding schools create problems for teachers and teacher satisfaction is low. It was found in the study that the teachers were not satisfied with the low readiness and academic achievement of the regional boarding school students, the insufficient school-family cooperation, and the additional responsibilities of the boarding school such as study and night shift (İnal & Sadık, 2014).

There is not enough accommodation for the teachers assigned to the regional boarding school. The fact that most of the teachers also fulfill their teaching and educational duties in the regional

boarding school reduces their effectiveness in the classroom (Ak & Sayıl, 2006). As a result of the research in which school administrators and regional boarding school teachers participated, it was determined that there was no computer software to support the special needs of the administration, hospital equipment and medical equipment were insufficient, and electricity and water cuts were experienced in schools and gymnasiums. At the same time, it was found that there are problems such as the need for support personnel such as nurses and security guards, the limited accommodation options for the personnel, and the teachers' feeling of having to pay extra tuition fees (Aydın & Köroğlu, 2009).

An important problem of the regional boarding school is the lack of communication and interest of the parents of the students in the school. In many studies, it has been determined that parents are indifferent to the school, and that the cooperation and solidarity between the school and the family is insufficient. However, another issue has come to the fore, suggesting that these problems are not only due to the indifference of the families. The remoteness of the regional boarding schools has made it very difficult for parents to communicate with students and schools. For this reason, it would not be correct to associate the family's inability to communicate adequately with the school only with the indifference of the families. It is observed that the limited access of the parents to the said schools creates a communication problem between the school and the family.

Considering the effect of family members on the academic success of the child, although studying away from the family environment is a problem in itself for children, the lack of communication of families with school and therefore with children brings this problem to light (Demirtaş, 2007).

There are studies showing that some regional boarding schools do not have sufficient physical facilities or that there is no standard. In these studies; It has been stated that there are deficiencies in the gym, hobby workshops or multi-purpose hall, therefore, students do not have enough opportunities to engage in educational and social activities outside the classroom (Karataş, 2006; Gökyer, 2011; İnal & Sadık, 2014). It is stated that schools should be suitable places in terms of physical order, appearance, usability and health, but it is argued that besides these minimum conditions, schools should be attractive places for children.

The theoretical information and research results provided reveal the place of regional boarding schools in the education system and the problems they face from different perspectives. On the other hand, no research has been encountered in the related literature that directly examines regional boarding schools in terms of equality in education. What are the characteristics of the students in regional boarding schools and what disadvantages they have in regional boarding schools, what advantages or disadvantages they offer compared to regular schools are very important. In this study, which was carried out to explain the academic perseverance of the students, it was observed that the disadvantages experienced negatively affected this scope and the academic success was low. Being away from family causes students to experience anxiety and stress disorders, and what these disorders directly affect is academic success.

In other words, within the scope of the fair dimension of educational equality, the qualifications of the students attending regional boarding schools, the status of education and living conditions in terms of the inclusive dimension of educational equality were observed. Considering that one of the most important duties of regional boarding schools is to provide education services to disadvantaged groups in the society who have difficulty in getting education, it is considered very important to look at these schools in terms of educational equality. Although it is thought to have many disadvantages, this system, which allows students who cannot receive education to receive education, also offers very important advantages in some respects. The most important of these advantages is that students who know how to stand on their own feet and who have reached a certain academic level are left to the future.

1.2. The Importance of Regional Boarding Secondary Schools in Success

Boarding schools are considered as educational institutions that can compensate for the negative conditions for the school success of disadvantaged students with additional opportunities. Institutions that Erving Goffman (1961) defined as “total institutions” train students in full-time boarding schools. These institutions are designed to provide both resocialization and enhanced learning and teaching outcomes. With its daily routine, discipline and guidance to fulfill this task, it makes a new lifestyle a habit for students. An education taken under difficult conditions is more important than a life without education (Yılmaz, 2014).

On the other hand, it is prevented from being under the influence of cultures that are not compatible with the school culture in order to minimize the connection of the student with the outside for a long time, or if he is affected before school life, he abandons these habits over time. The student, who lives with only teachers and administrators, does not see the bad features of external life and completes his education efficiently. This is especially important for adolescence. The reason for this is explained as the situation in which the student is highly influenced by his environment during adolescence.

In this context, regional boarding schools include facilities such as study halls and sports infrastructure that disadvantaged students need in order to be successful in their schools, cultural products such as textbooks, support resources, films and theater, tutoring services and long-term teacher interest, and comprehensive libraries. At the same time, it encourages students to study only because there are few distractions in these schools.

1.2.1. Regional Boarding Secondary Schools in the Turkish Education System

The idea of student dormitory in Turkey has existed since the Ottoman Empire. Since the first years of the Republic, intensive efforts have been made to expand education in the country. YİBOs, especially the opening of "orphanages" under the leadership of the Minister of National Education Mustafa Necat, and the opening of "orphanages" in rural areas, in hard-to-reach areas and geographical regions where transportation is difficult, facilitates the students' coming to school.

With the establishment of regional boarding secondary schools, female students began to be accepted as boarders. Since 1942, boarding or daytime “Village Regional Schools” have begun to be established; Article 1 of the regional schools regulation, which was prepared in 1962 depending on the primary education location and the local education location, "Boarding Primary Schools are opened in the villages where there are many villages close to each other and in the regions where there are house groups." expanded in accordance with Art. Article 25 of the National Education Basic Law No. 1739 dated 1973 ensured the continuation of the establishment of YİBOs.

While there were 280 thousand students in 602 YİBOs in the 2007-2008 academic year, there are 429 YİBOs operating in 72 provinces throughout Turkey in the 2013-14 academic year, and 159.053 students (80,775 girls and 78,178 boys) receive education and 8937 teachers work in these schools. . The main reason for this decrease is the return to bussed education. Since the 2012-13 academic year, the duration of compulsory education in Turkey (4+4+4) has increased to 12 years, so the name of YİBOs has been differentiated as Regional Boarding Secondary Schools (YBO). In parallel with the decrease in the number of these schools in recent years, the number of students studying here has started to decrease.

1.2.2. Numerical Statistics of Regional Boarding Secondary Schools

Table 1. Number of YBO Students by Year

Year	Number of School	Total Student Numbers	Number of Male Students	Number of Female Students
2000-2001	247	131 161	95 297	35 864
2001-2002	275	139 971	99 865	40 106
2002-2003	285	140 779	97 495	43 284
2003-2004	289	144 446	98 598	45 848
2004-2005	299	142 788	95 743	47 045
2005-2006	300	135 524	88 690	46 834
2006-2007	603	282 132	167 988	114 144
2007-2008	603	267 516	156 846	110 670
2008-2009	593	262 838	149 051	113 787

2009-2010	574	265 285	145 695	119 590
2010-2011	539	247 563	131 874	115 689
2011-2012	495	212 894	112 355	100 539
2012-2013	468	171 854	86 540	85 314
2013-2014	429	159 053	78 178	80 375
2014-2015	387	117 305	60 606	56 699
2015-2016	341	94 455	48 784	45 671
2016-2017	325	89 979	46 498	43 481
2017-2018	312	78 262	40 929	37 333

Reference: (Çangir, 2019; 26).

If Table 1 is examined, 247 schools 131,161 students in the 2000-2001 academic year, 275 schools 139,971 students in the 2001-2002 academic year, 285 schools 140,779 students in the 2002-2003 academic year, 299 schools 142 in the 2004-2005 academic year, 788 students, 300 schools 135,524 students in 2005-2006 academic year, 603 schools 282,132 students in 2006-2007 academic year, 603 schools 267,516 students in 2007-2008 academic year, 593 schools 262,838 students in 2008-2009 academic year, In the 2009-2010 academic year, 574 schools with 265,285 students, in the 2010-2011 academic year 539 schools with 247,563 students, in the 2011-2012 academic year 495 schools with 212,894 students, in the 2012-2013 academic year 468 schools, 171,854 students, 2013- In the 2014 academic year, 429 schools, 159,053 students, in the 2014-2015 academic year 387 schools 117,305 students, in the 2015-2016 academic year 341 schools 94,455 students, in the 2016-2017 academic year 325 schools 89,979 students In the 2017-2018 academic year, 78,262 students in 312 schools continued their attendance to Regional Boarding Primary Schools and to Regional Boarding Secondary Schools after the 2012-2013 academic year. It was observed that the number of YİBOs, which was observed as 603 in the 2007-2008 academic year, decreased to 312 in the 2017-2018 academic year. It is observed that the number of YBOs has started to decrease in recent years as a result of the widespread use of transported education and the increase in the number of classrooms and schools.

2. RELATED RESEARCHES

Kılıç (2001) observed significant differences between primary and regional boarding schools within the scope of his study titled "Comparison of the level of realization of social functions of

the Regional Boarding Primary School and other primary schools”. As a result of the research, it has been determined that the teachers in regional boarding schools have less experience, there are fewer female teachers in YİBO and there are fewer female students.

Halicı (2005), in his study titled “Examination of aggression tendencies and self-concepts of 12-14 year old children attending Regional Boarding Primary Schools and living with their families”, found the place where the child lives, age, gender, the reason for coming to the regional boarding primary school, how many people in the room. It has been found that the stay of the students creates a difference in the scores obtained in the aggression dimension.

In the study carried out by Ak and Sayıl (2006), academic perseverance and success, perceived social support levels, attitudes towards school and behavioral adjustment problems of students from different school types (boarding school, bussed school and regular school) were discussed. The results of the research showed that the level of adaptation of the students in boarding schools, especially in the first level of primary education, is lower than the others, and behavioral problems are higher than the students in the second level of boarding. However, this difference was not observed in students studying in the transported education system. However, it was found that family structure, attitude towards school and perceived social support did not tire students' academic achievement.

Demirtaş (2007) examined the relationship between the level of social support, loneliness level and coping with stress experienced by primary school 8th grade students. As a result of the research, no significant difference was found between the level of loneliness according to gender, perceived social support from family, friends and teachers and encountering stress. However, no significant difference was found between the economic status of the families and the perceived social support from friends and teachers.

Yılmaz (2014), in his research titled “Student Opinions on the Operation of Regional Boarding Schools”; Various problems are encountered in these schools, where students continue their lives as well as their education. These are the problems related to the quality of education and the society's view of the school, personnel and student-parent problems, and the inadequacy of services related to the financial and physical condition of the school. Boarding schools are declining in popularity because success rates decline each year and students come to their schools with different education options. According to the results of this study, the number of students in regional boarding schools is decreasing. Students do not want to go to regional boarding schools and parents do not want to send them to regional boarding schools.

According to the results obtained within the scope of Aydın et al.'s (2018) study; Academic self-efficacy and emotional self-efficacy, which are the two sub-variables of the self-efficacy variable, were found to be significant predictors of academic achievement. Within the scope of this result, it is observed that the effect of academic self-efficacy on academic performance is positive, while the effect of emotional self-efficacy is negative. This finding is consistent with studies in the

literature showing the relationship between academic self-efficacy, emotional self-efficacy and academic achievement.

Studies have shown that when the level of perceived social support from family and friends increases, that is, if education continues at home and in the family environment, there is an increase in aggression, test anxiety, anxiety disorders, depression, stress, loneliness and professional immaturity, academic success and self-confidence. Studies in general; It has been shown that girls receive higher levels of social support from family and friends than boys.

3. CONCLUSION

Within the scope of the information obtained as a result of the study, it has been observed that the regional boarding schools in Turkey benefit the education equality phenomenon in terms of entering the education life of the students living in the rural areas and positively affect the academic determination of the students in this direction. In the study, regional boarding schools were considered as institutions established to provide education to students living in residential areas with a low population and no school. There have been changes over time in regional boarding schools that provide education in line with certain conditions. The first change observed within the scope of these changes can be expressed as the transformation of YİBOs into YBOs or the fact that girls have also started to be educated over time.

As a result of the literature review, it was concluded that YBO affects academic achievement negatively in some studies and positively in some studies. The reason for the difference experienced here is the stress, anxiety, longing, etc., caused by being separated from the family in some studies. It was concluded that emotions negatively affect academic achievement. In some studies, it is thought that academic perseverance increases due to the fact that childhood was separated from the family at a young age and stood on its own feet, learning about life at a young age, and the absence of any distractions other than education.

In this context, it can be concluded that academic achievement decreases under some conditions and increases under other conditions. Family can be given as the most important variable affecting this.

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